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Dissatisfaction with the Landscape of the Place of Living in the Italian Regions

About 18.6% of respondents are dissatisfied with the landscape

Istat calculates dissatisfaction with the landscape of the place of living. This indicator considers the percentage of people aged over 14 who declare that the landscape of the place they live is affected by evident degradation out of the total number of people aged 14 and over. The data refers to the period between 2014 and 2022 for the Italian regions.

Ranking of Italian regions by value of dissatisfaction with the landscape of the place of living in the Italian regions in 2022. Campania is in first place for dissatisfaction with the landscape of the place of living with a value of 31.3, followed by Calabria with a value equal to 30.5 units and from Sicily with a value equal to 30.4 units. In the middle of the table we find Piedmont with a value of 17.1 units, followed by Lombardy and Tuscany with a value of 16.1 units. Umbria closes the ranking with a value of 11.7 units, followed by Friuli Venezia Giulia with a value of 9.7 units, and Trentino Alto Adige with a value of 8.1 units.

Ranking of the Italian regions by percentage change in the value of dissatisfaction with the landscape of the place of living in the Italian regions between 2014 and 2022. Sicily is in first place by value of the percentage change in the value of dissatisfaction with the landscape of the place of life in the Italian regions between 2014 and 2022 with a value equal to +31.6% corresponding to a variation between 23.1 units up to 30.4 units. Valle d'Aosta is in second place with a variation equal to +28.57% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 11.2 units in 2014 up to a value of 14.4 units in 2022. Tuscany follows in third placed with a variation equal to +21.97% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 13.2 units up to a value of 16.1 units. Piedmont is mid-table with a value equal to +2.4% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 16.7 units up to a value of 17.1 units. Umbria follows with a value of -0.85% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 11.8 units up to an amount of 11.7 units. Puglia follows with a value equal to -1.19% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 25.3 units up to a value of 25 units. Among the last places is Veneto with a value equal to -15.7% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 17.2 units up to a value of 14.5 units. Friuli Venezia Giulia follows with a value equal to an amount of -16.38% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 17.2 units up to a value of 14.5 units. Abruzzo follows with a variation equal to -30.32% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 22.1 units up to a value of 15.4 units.

Dissatisfaction with the living landscape in the Italian macro-regions between 2014 and 2022. Dissatisfaction with the living landscape decreased in the North with a value equal to -5.06%, in the North-West with an amount equal to -4.02%, in the North-East with a value equal to -7.30% and in the South with a value equal to -0.74%. However, there are macro-regions in which the value of dissatisfaction with the living landscape has grown, namely the Center with +9.14%, the South with a value equal to +6.15% and the Islands with a value equal to at +22.13%. On average, the value of

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dissatisfaction with the living landscape grew in the Italian macro-regions from an amount of 20.47 units up to a value of 21.31 units or equal to an amount of +4.12%.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Below we present a clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Two clusters are identified as follows:

- Cluster 1: Sicily, Lazio, Puglia, Campania, Calabria, Basilicata, Sardinia, Liguria;
- Cluster 2: Emilia Romagna, Friuli Venezia Giulia, Marche, Veneto, Tuscany, Valle d'Aosta, Umbria, Trentino Alto Adige, Lombardy, Piedmont, Molise, Abruzzo.

From the cluster point of view we can see the following ordering: $C1 > C2$. Cluster C1 is essentially made up of the southern regions with the addition of Lazio and Liguria. The only southern region absent in cluster 1 and present in cluster 2 is Abruzzo. Cluster 2 is instead made up of the central-northern regions with the addition of Abruzzo. It therefore follows that the southern regions are characterized by a high level of dissatisfaction with the landscape of the place where they live. This value turns out to be counterfactual. In fact, generally the southern regions tend to welcome a very high level of tourists, especially in the summer periods, who choose those places precisely for landscape reasons. It therefore follows that southerners are highly dissatisfied with the quality of the landscape excluding tourist resorts and therefore above all with reference to inland towns and non-coastal cities. The case of Campania is particularly serious, although it is characterized by significant scenic beauty, where around 30% of the population declares themselves dissatisfied with the landscape.

Conclusions. The value of dissatisfaction with the landscape of the place of living appears to be unchanged on average between 2014 and 2022. However, this value increased in the central-southern regions and decreased in the central-northern regions. It follows that the quality of life is compromised in the southern regions from a landscape point of view. The reasons relating to the growth of dissatisfaction with the landscape of the place of living can essentially be traced back to illegal construction, poor civic culture and also to the action of eco-mafias which have certainly reduced the usability of the landscape in the southern regions. We must also consider that the landscape must be considered a scarce good. In fact, the landscape is excessively used for construction reasons with perverse effects both on the level of quality of life of the population and for issues of the hydro-geological safety of the territories.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Appendix

